

QUIZ**LAST NAME: DENG****FIRST NAME: ACHAI****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author used Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice 2019

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. In which of the following sentences is punctuation misused?

- Punctuation is essential to meaning, it should be used appropriately.¹**
- The discussion on equal rights, however, was not as fruitful as expected.
- We will choose from the following topics: politics, law, and education.
- Finally, the lecturer will expound on the differences between UK and US English.

2. Which sentence best describes the purpose of the European Commission's English Style.

¹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (Brussels: Publications Office of the European Union, 2011), 16.

- It aims to clarify writing guidelines in Standard English, including punctuation, spelling, abbreviations, and verbs.
 - It explains aspects of British English and lays out guidelines for translating other European languages into English.
 - It discusses the conventions of writing in standard English and their application in writing for the European Commission.²**
 - It principally aims to be a handy writing guide for native and non-native writers of the European Commission.
3. **Walter argues that all bear attacks are the result of humans surprising the bear. How can he strengthen his argument?**
- By giving evidence of his claim.
 - By making use of a qualifier.³**
 - By adding a strong opinion to his claim.
 - By giving directives on avoiding mountain bears.
4. **What should Adebayo include in his essay to reflect logical organization?**
- Specific details that support the main point.⁴**
 - Clear, elaborate formulations.
 - Word choices that emphasize meaning.
 - Smooth-reading sentences.

² European Commission, 1.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Massachusetts: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1999), 121.

⁴ Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer, 21.

5. **By which of the following ways can Mary avoid plagiarism in her assignments?**

- Citing information that is common knowledge.
- Paraphrasing by rearranging the structure and substituting the word choice of the original.
- Asking a close friend to write on her behalf.
- Citing the methods and experiments of other writers.**⁵

6. **When considering a research question, which of the following factors may add to the question's acceptance?**

- The question is easy for anyone to answer.
- The question has already been answered by other researchers.**⁶
- The answer to the question cannot be plausibly disproved.
- There is not sufficient evidence available to answer the question.

7. **What is the primary aim of most academic research?**

- To generate knowledge that can solve practical problems.
- To satisfy an intellectual itch whose study will benefit humanity.
- To better the understanding of various subjects.**⁷
- To awaken in the public interest in specific topics.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 55.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 21.

⁷ Turabian, 16.

8. Which of the following set of words, sentences, or phrases should Celine avoid in writing for a British company?
- ‘The boy kicked the ball.’
 - Analyse, organisation, per cent.
 - Dear Mrs. Smith:**⁸
 - Sulfur, billion, disk.
9. Chipo has noticed a minor grammatical error in a direct quote she has cited. What would be best for her to do?
- Correct the error with comment.
 - Add the word “sic” in brackets next to the error.
 - Use ellipses to omit the erroneous part.
 - Paraphrase the quotation.**⁹
10. Which of the following best describes the structure of a paragraph?
- Introduction, body, conclusion.
 - Beginning, middle, end.
 - Topic sentence, supporting sentences, critical conclusion.**¹⁰
 - Opening sentence, analytical sentences, closing sentence.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 30.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 48.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 3.

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